

POSITIVE SOCIAL MEDIA TRANSFORMATION THROUGH SMALL VOICES MOVEMENT

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Cyberbullying, Fear of Missing Out (FOMO), exposure to negative content and hoaxes, as well as susceptibility to personal data breaches are negative aspects brought about by social media (socmed). Despite being the primary source of information for Indonesian netizens in the last three years [1], users reached 60.4% of the population of 278 million as of January 2023, predominantly among the 13-34 age group or the younger generation [2].

Initially serving as a platform for people to interact despite distances, time, and different locations, social media has transformed into a modern colosseum. It's where people gather to witness various spectacles, whether pseudo-debates in comment sections or collectively indulging in absurd viral news. If this habit continues unchecked, where will the Indonesian youth end up? Consumed by and spreading hoaxes, sowing hatred in every status update without offering solutions, and easily echoing without profound learning, solely based on watching conspiracy videos.

Another issue not to be overlooked is the mental health disturbances caused by social media engagement. The largest group of socmed users, teenagers and young adults, needs careful attention. This is in line with reports that 1 in 3 Indonesian teenagers (aged 10-17) experience mental health issues, equivalent to 15.5 million individuals [3].

The negative issues arising from improper internet, especially social media, usage must be addressed. Otherwise, the younger generation, the nation's future, won't be ready to embrace technological advancements as the most potent educational tool. The increasingly accessible information should ideally be utilized for learning outside formal environments.

Hence, a positive social media transformation is needed. There is a need for reform or a return to the original purpose of social media usage. Thus, the Small Voices Movement is born, a gathering of spirits among a small fraction of Facebook users to voice their thoughts and feelings. Through statutes containing knowledge sharing

and experiences, it's hoped to foster healthy discussions in comment sections and expand networks with people from diverse backgrounds.

The Birth of the Small Voices Movement

The Small Voices Movement didn't emerge overnight. It was initiated by a young woman named Eva, who initially proposed the Writing Challenge. Currently, Eva is involved in the start-up world with a focus on volunteerism and social issues. She envisions the Writing Challenge as a platform for individuals to express themselves more purposefully through beneficial and positively entertaining statuses.

The Writing Challenge involves a daily writing challenge for Facebook users who wish to participate. Last July 2023, the #JulyWritingChallenge was formed, providing a platform for 30 young individuals from diverse backgrounds to express their opinions. Ranging from simple questions like 'What are your love languages?' to complex ones like 'Should Indonesian women adopt feminism? Why?'

Various opinions surfaced, sparking a domino effect. Participants read each other's opinions, leading to healthy discussions. Because of the positive response to #JulyWritingChallenge, it continued this month with #AugustWritingChallenge focusing on societal topics.

The Small Voices Movement stands as one solution to address the challenges of Technology in Education, transforming habits across various demographics in using social media platforms. Facebook is the primary focus of this movement due to its extensive user base, ranging from youth to elderly individuals [4]. This marks a concrete step towards using technology as an alternative educational platform, promoting collaborative learning, stimulating creativity, and raising awareness about social issues.

Technology as an Alternative Educational Platform

The Writing Challenge presents various questions that serve as alternative avenues for learning beyond classroom walls. There's a wealth of knowledge in the world, and it's a pity if only a few can access it. One of the questions that prompts people to share their stories is as follows.

Stories from different cultures emerge. From Sumatra to Sulawesi, each has its uniqueness and characteristics. Here are some screenshots to demonstrate that when social media is used appropriately, it can become an alternative educational platform.

People living in Sumatra, Kalimantan, and Sulawesi get to know what Mapati and Mudun Lemah are. Those on Java Island learn about Bekarang from South Sumatra, Uang Panai from Makassar, and Tepuk Tepung Tawar from the Malay culture. This is the advantage of social media; it brings together people who are far apart.

Collaborative Learning in the Digital Age

Through this Writing Challenge, a collaborative learning space is formed in the virtual world. When someone shares an opinion, others can respond with different helpful information. Here are some other questions with responses from two netizens.

Every human has their blind spots. A combination of knowledge, experiences, dreams, upbringing by parents and teachers, and social circles shapes their answers. Therefore, through collaborative learning, someone's blind spots become clearer, allowing them to see from different perspectives.

Stimulating Creativity and Addressing Social Issues

With thought-provoking questions, participants become more sensitive and critical towards social issues in Indonesia. Perhaps they were merely spectators of various news before, but now they contribute, at least by fostering sympathy and concern to explore these issues. Here are some questions that have been asked and answered by dozens of participants spread across Indonesia.

Some participants who were unfamiliar with terms like feminism, nature, childfree, LGBTQ, and honorary teachers were encouraged to surf briefly about these terms. They become more aware and pay more attention to life in their surroundings. This should be continued so that the younger generation doesn't become mere spectators with social media as their circus.

Replication of the Small Voices Movement Spirit

It is hoped that the spirit and dreams of the Small Voices Movement will be replicated by various stakeholders, both from the private and public sectors, including educational actors and Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs). Create an ecosystem where people can speak regardless of gender, religion, ethnicity, wealth, education, or social status. This is important because Indonesian society is composed of complex layers.

Social media, now easily accessible by anyone, should be utilized to truly ground democracy, ensuring that corporate interests do not drown out the people's voices. Economic and educational equalization may still be challenging and require a long process. However, social media is a powerful weapon in the right hands. Let's realize

the equal voices of the people, where their ideas are expressed and listened to equally.

However, strict monitoring is required in the implementation of this replication. One important rule is to guide netizens to share beneficial things that can increase the insights and sympathies of readers. Thus, the real benefits of technology use in education can be achieved.

Conclusion

In an era where social media increasingly dominates life, negative impacts such as cyberbullying, FOMO, negative content, and spreading hoaxes have been revealed. However, this challenge is not just a technological issue but a call to change the behaviour and perceptions of Indonesian society towards social media. The Small Voices Movement emerges as one concrete solution. Through this movement, social media is expected to become an alternative educational tool, fostering collaborative learning, stimulating creativity, and raising awareness of social issues. With a focus on positive education and meaningful participation, this movement invites social media users, especially the younger generation, to use technology wisely. Despite significant challenges in managing social media, its positive potential can still be achieved with commitment and joint efforts from various stakeholders.

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